

Supplementary Materials

A Three-Pronged Validation Framework for AI-Based Emotion Extraction

Appendix A: Validation Statistics

This appendix presents the core validation evidence for the LETA (Longitudinal Emotion Trajectory Analysis) framework. Full methodology is described in the main text; data files and analysis scripts are available at GitHub: [RayanBVasse/LETA: Longitudinal Emotion Trajectory Analysis](#).

A.1 Validation 1: AI-Human Convergence (RW3D Dataset)

Objective: Compare AI-extracted emotions against authors' self-reported emotional states to characterize the relationship between expressed and felt emotion.

Dataset: Real World Worry Dataset (RW3D; Kleinberg et al., 2020; van der Vegt et al., 2023); N = 1,152 participants; free-text pandemic worry narratives with concurrent 9-point Likert emotion ratings.

Method: NRC Emotion Lexicon applied to narratives. AI-extracted primary emotion compared against self-reported primary emotion.

Table A.1: Categorical Classification Performance

Metric	Observed	Chance	Improvement	<i>p</i>
Exact match (8 emotions)	33.5%	12.5%	2.7×	< .001
Top-2 match	58.3%	25.0%	2.3×	< .001

Table A.2: Dimensional Correlations (AI-Extracted vs. Self-Report)

AI Emotion	Self-Report	<i>r</i>	95% CI	<i>p</i>
Anger	Anger	.209	[.15, .27]	< .001
Disgust	Disgust	.185	[.13, .24]	< .001
Fear	Anxiety	.175	[.12, .23]	< .001
Fear	Fear	.170	[.11, .23]	< .001
Sadness	Sadness	.161	[.10, .22]	< .001

Joy	Happiness	.157	[.10, .21]	< .001
<i>Mean</i>		.176		

Interpretation: Moderate categorical agreement (58.3% top-2) with weak dimensional correlations (mean $r = .18$) indicates that expressed emotion (what AI detects in text) and felt emotion (what humans consciously report) are related but distinct constructs sharing approximately 3% of variance.

A.2 Validation 2: Methodological Validity (Blog Corpus)

Objective: Assess convergent validity against established tools and discriminant validity against alternative approaches.

Dataset: Blog Authorship Corpus subset (Schler et al., 2006); 18,604 posts from 40 authors; temporal span 2001–2004.

Table A.3: Convergent and Discriminant Validity

Comparison	Mean r	Interpretation
LETA vs. SEANCE-NRC (same lexicon)	.869	Strong convergent validity
LETA vs. SEANCE-GALC (different lexicon)	.107	Expected divergence
LETA vs. Transformer classifier	.012	Different constructs
LETA valence vs. VADER sentiment	.286	Related constructs

Interpretation: Strong correlation with same-lexicon implementation ($r = .87$) confirms LETA correctly operationalizes the NRC lexicon. Weak correlations with different lexicons ($r = .11$) and transformer classifiers ($r = .12$) demonstrate that these approaches measure related but distinct aspects of emotional expression.

A.3 Validation 3: Naturalistic Application (Longitudinal Blog Analysis)

Objective: Examine whether extracted patterns show psychologically meaningful properties including archetype stability, trajectory consistency, and independence from demographic confounds.

Dataset: Blog Authorship Corpus extended subset; 32,799 posts from 100 authors; author metadata includes age (range: 13–48, $M = 25.8$) and gender (56% male, 44% female).

Table A.4: Four Emotional Clustering

Archetype	n (%)	Trust z	Joy z	Fear z	Signature
C-1	36 (36%)	-0.53	-0.58	-0.20	Below-average all categories
C-2	28 (28%)	-0.15	+0.11	-0.59	Low negative, moderate optimism
C-3	19 (19%)	+0.82	+1.18	+0.15	Elevated positive affect
C-4	17 (17%)	+0.45	-0.27	+1.25	Elevated negative emotions

Note. Archetypes identified via K-means clustering ($k = 4$); silhouette score = .239. ANOVA confirmed significant between-archetype differences: $F(3, 96) = 3.86, p = .012$.

Table A.5: Trajectory Stability

Pattern	% Authors	Classification Criteria
Stable	75%	Volatility in bottom 3 quartiles; no significant trend
Oscillating	18%	CV in top 25% with direction changes
Erratic	5%	CV in top 5% (extreme variability)
Directional (improving/declining)	2%	Significant slope + consistent Q-diff

Interpretation: 75% of authors maintained stable emotional expression patterns over multi-year periods, suggesting emotional expression functions as a trait-like individual characteristic.

Table A.6: Variance Decomposition

Source	Emotion Variance Explained
Demographics alone (age, gender)	4.9%
Topics alone (12-dimension LDA)	53.3%
Combined (demographics + topics)	54.2%
Unexplained (individual differences)	45.8%

Note. Demographics explain only 4.9% of emotional variance. Chi-square tests confirm gender is independent of affect typology ($\chi^2 = 0.18, p = .67$) and age shows no association with typology ($t = 0.06, p = .95$).

Table A.7: Consolidated Validation Evidence

Validation	Dataset	Key Metric	Value	Interpretation
1	RW3D	Top-2 match	58.3%	2.3× chance
1	RW3D	Mean dimensional r	.176	~3% shared variance
2	Blog corpus	SEANCE-NRC convergent	.869	Strong
2	Blog corpus	Transformer discriminant	.012	Different constructs

3	Blog corpus	Trajectory stability	75%	Trait-like
3	Blog corpus	Unexplained variance	45.8%	Individual signal

Appendix B: Technical Specifications

This appendix provides technical details necessary for replication. Complete code and data are available at [[GitHub repository URL](#)].

B.1 Software Environment

Table B.1: Core Dependencies

Package	Version	Purpose
Python	3.10+	Runtime environment
pandas	2.0+	Data manipulation
numpy	1.24+	Numerical operations
scikit-learn	1.3+	Clustering, validation metrics
scipy	1.11+	Statistical tests
gensim	4.3+	LDA topic modeling
nltk	3.8+	Tokenization, stopwords

Reproducibility: All analyses use fixed random seeds (seed = 42 for clustering). Docker container with frozen package versions available in repository.

B.2 NRC Emotion Lexicon

Source: Mohammad & Turney (2013); version 0.92

Coverage: ~14,182 English words mapped to 8 emotion categories

Table B.2: Emotion Dimensions

Dimension	Definition	Example Words
Anger	Hostile, aggressive affect	fury, rage, annoyed, bitter
Anticipation	Forward-looking expectation	expect, hope, eager, ready
Disgust	Revulsion, rejection	gross, nasty, revolting, vile
Fear	Threat-related anxiety	scared, terrified, panic, dread
Joy	Positive hedonic affect	happy, delighted, pleased, cheerful
Sadness	Loss-related negative affect	sad, grief, sorrow, miserable
Surprise	Unexpected event response	amazed, astonished, shocked
Trust	Confidence, reliability	believe, faith, confident, reliable

Scoring: For each text, emotion score = (count of words matching emotion category) / (total word count). Scores normalized to [0, 1] range.

Limitations: Lexicon-based approach does not capture negation, sarcasm, or context-dependent meaning.

B.3 Clustering Parameters

K-Means Configuration (Archetype Identification):

```
n_clusters = 4 # Determined by silhouette analysis

init = 'k-means++' # Smart centroid initialization

n_init = 10 # Number of initializations

max_iter = 300 # Maximum iterations

random_state = 42 # Reproducibility seed
```

Table B.3: Silhouette Analysis Results

<i>k</i>	Silhouette Score	Interpretation
2	.289	Optimal for binary High/Low Expression typology
3	.296	Inflated by outlier singleton
4	.239	Selected for descriptive granularity
5	.178	Over-partitioned

B.4 Statistical Tests Reference

Table B.4: Tests Used in Validation

Test	Application	Assumptions Checked
Pearson r	AI-human emotion correlation	Linearity, normality
Independent t-test	Typology emotion differences	Equal variance (Levene's)
Chi-square	Archetype × demographics	Expected cell counts > 5
ANOVA	Between-archetype differences	Homogeneity of variance
Silhouette score	Cluster validation	—
Cohen's d	Effect size for t-tests	—

Multiple comparison correction: Bonferroni correction applied where multiple tests conducted on same dataset.

Appendix C: GitHub Repository Contents

C.1 Repository Structure

LETA-Validation/

```
|— README.md
|
|— requirements.txt
|
|— LICENSE (MIT)
|
|
|— data/
|  |— validation1_rw3d/
|  |  |— pillar1_verification_results.csv
|  |— validation2_convergent/
|  |  |— leta_seance_emolex_correlations.csv
|  |  |— leta_seance_galc_correlations.csv
|  |  |— transformer_emotions.csv
|  |— validation3_longitudinal/
|  |  |— pillar3_author_clusters.csv
|  |  |— pillar3_trajectories.csv
|  |  |— pillar3_variance_decomposition.csv
|
|
|— lexicons/
|  |— NRC-Emotion-Lexicon-v0.92.txt
|
```

```

├─ scripts/
|   ├─ 01_validation1_ai_human_convergence.py
|   ├─ 02_validation2_methodological_validity.py
|   └─ 03_validation3_naturalistic_application.py
|   └─ utils/
|       └─ emotion_extraction.py
|
└─ outputs/
    ├─ figures/
    └─ tables/

```

C.2 Data Availability

Table C.1: Dataset Access

Dataset	Availability	Access
RW3D Dataset	Public	https://osf.io/9b85r/
Blog Authorship Corpus	Public	http://u.cs.biu.ac.il/~koppel/BlogCorpus.htm
NRC Emotion Lexicon	Public	https://saifmohammad.com/WebPages/NRC-Emotion-Lexicon.htm
Analysis code	Open source	[GitHub repository URL] (MIT License)

Reproducibility commitment: All random seeds documented; intermediate outputs archived; prompts fully specified.

Appendix D: Example Narrative Arc Reports

This appendix presents example outputs from LETA's trajectory analysis capability, demonstrating how the framework characterizes individual emotional patterns over time. These examples use participants from the RW3D dataset (3-wave longitudinal design) and the Blog Authorship Corpus.

D.1 Example: Recovery Arc (RW3D Participant 755)

Dataset: RW3D (Waves 1–3)

Pattern: Strong Improver

Table D.1: Emotional Trajectory

Wave	Sentiment	Summary
1	-0.42	Predominantly negative; elevated fear-anxiety cluster
2	-0.18	Reduction in negative affect; lower fear and anger
3	+0.05	Neutral-to-slightly positive; continued reduction

Interpretation: Monotonic improvement from acute distress to emotional stabilization. Topic drift follows consistent progression: acute uncertainty → adaptive management → recovery orientation.

D.2 Example: Stable Flat Trajectory (RW3D Participant 175)

Dataset: RW3D (Waves 1–3)

Pattern: Flatliner (neutral-stable)

Table D.2: Emotional Trajectory

Wave	Sentiment	Summary
1	-0.05	Near-neutral; minimal emotional signal
2	-0.03	Stable neutrality; marginally negative
3	-0.04	Essentially unchanged

Interpretation: This participant shows topic stasis with negligible thematic or emotional evolution. Cross-wave cosine similarity (0.90–0.93) indicates extremely high semantic consistency. This profile demonstrates LETA's ability to characterize low-variance trajectories.

D.3 Trajectory Pattern Distribution

Across the full validation sample, the following trajectory patterns were observed:

- Strong Improver: ~5% of participants (recovery arc)
- Strong Decliner: ~5% of participants (erosion arc)
- Oscillator: ~15% of participants (high variability, no clear direction)
- Stable Negative: ~20% of participants (chronic negative affect)
- Stable Neutral/Positive: ~55% of participants (resilience or detachment)

Note: These narrative arc reports are generated programmatically from LETA emotion extraction outputs. They demonstrate the framework's capacity for individual-level longitudinal characterization.

Table A.8: LETA vs Transformer Per-Emotion Correlations (Blog Corpus, n = 18,545)

Emotion	r	p
sadness	.024	.001
anger	.018	.015
joy	.017	.022
disgust	.014	.060
fear	.008	.282
surprise	-.009	.206
Mean	.012	—

Note. Near-zero correlations indicate lexicon-based (LETA) and transformer-based emotion extraction measure largely non-overlapping aspects of text. Lexicons detect explicit emotion vocabulary; transformers detect contextual semantic patterns. Only sadness reached significance at $p < .01$.

Table A.9: Transformer vs Self-Report Correlations (RW3D, n=1,152)

Transformer	Self-Report	r	p
anger	anger	.268	< .001
disgust	disgust	.148	< .001
fear	fear	.243	< .001
fear	anxiety	.285	< .001
joy	happiness	.223	< .001
sadness	sadness	.103	< .001
Mean		.212	

Note. Transformer = DistilRoBERTa fine-tuned on emotion detection (Hartmann et al., 2023). Transformer shows modestly stronger correlations than lexicon (mean $r = .212$ vs $.176$) but both explain < 5% of variance in self-reported emotion, confirming the expressed-felt gap is method-universal

Table A.10: LETA vs SEANCE-GALC Correlations (Blog Corpus, n=18,604)

Emotion	r	p
anger	.192	< .001
fear	.167	< .001
joy	.088	< .001
sadness	.070	< .001
surprise	.066	< .001
disgust	.057	< .001
Mean	.107	

Note. GALC = Geneva Affect Label Coder, a different emotion lexicon than NRC. Weak correlations (mean $r = .107$) demonstrate that different lexicons, though both word-based, measure related but distinct aspects of emotional expression.